

TARO LEAF CHIPS WITH HONEY ADDITION TO HEAL GASTRIC DISEASE

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Abstract

Utilization of taro leaves as a healthy chips to cure gastric disease. The purpose of this study is to determine the benefits of taro leaves (*Colocasia esculenta*) which can be used as a natural ingredient for making healthy chips healing gastric. The research method is literature study, experiment with the making of taro leaf chips (*Colocasia esculenta*) and tested to two mice (*Mus musculus*) and by giving chips daunt base (*Colocasia esculenta*) to the respondent consisting of 15 students of SMK N 3 Jakarta, the safety test used to know that the taro leaf chips (*Colocasia esculenta*) is safe to be used as an alternative to healing gastric, efficacy test by giving the same intake to three samples of 30 grams at one meal, given after lunch and after dinner with the excuse to be able to neutralize the food that has been consumed. The first day of the three samples consumed no negative effects. However, after a week respondents felt that there was a change and the positive effect since consuming taro leaves chips (*Colocasia esculenta*) also there is no negative effects on respondents after consuming the taro leaf chips (*Colocasia esculenta*). This shows that the taro leaf chips (*Colocasia esculenta*) can cure gastric disease.

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1.Introduction

Indonesia is a country with great food potential. Various types of food plants and medicinal plants can be cultivated in Indonesia. Indonesia has 25,000-30,000 species of plants which constitute 10% of the world's plants and 90% of Asian plants [1]. Based on Dewoto (2007), as many as 7,000 species of this amount are used by the Indonesian people as medicine. Various types of food and medicinal plants are produced to meet people's food needs. In addition to increasing the amount, fulfilling food needs can also be done by optimizing the use of diverse food sources. This is done as an effort to diversify food by utilizing available resources [2]. One type of local resource plant that can be used as a food alternative and easily cultivated is the type of taro plant (*Colocasia esculenta*).

Taro is a perennial plant that has fake tuber or stem which is actually a petiole. Taro generally can only grow in places that are not muddy or require sufficient watering [3]. In general, taro is a local food source of carbohydrates because in 100 grams of taro contains 145 Kcal of energy, 34.20 grams of carbohydrate, 0.40 grams of fat and 1.20 grams of protein. However, the use of

taro plants as a food consumption is considered less optimal, because people generally process taro as food only in the part of the tuber. And the exclusion of the nutrients in the whole section taro plant organs, such as the taro leaves. One of the plants that is very underutilized scientifically today is the leaf of *Colocasia esculenta* L. from Pare-Pare, South Sulawesi, which is used as a medicine for inflammation, purulent skin, blood defecation, boils, and burns with the chemical content of saponins, terpenes, terpenes, tannins, flavonoids, flobatanin, antraquinone, cardiac glycosides, and alkaloids [4].). A study researched that taro leaves have unusually large polyphenols and saponins. Behind the various contents that have taro leaves have the potential to be used as a healthy food that is good for the stomach.

Digestive tract disorders are one of the disorders that are often complained of and have become a public health problem. Among the many gastrointestinal disorders suffered in the community, the most common complaints found in the department of gastroenterology are complaints of dyspepsia, pain in the stomach, bloating and nausea, where the complaint is one of the typical symptoms of gastroenteritis ranging from acute to chronic [5]. Gastric disorders or better known as stomach ulcers (gastritis) often arise from habits in poor lifestyle. Gastritis which is known as heartburn is an upper gastrointestinal disease that is often complained of in the community and most commonly found in the gastroenterology section, it is estimated that almost all gastritis sufferers experience recurrence. One of the factors that can cause the appearance of symptoms of gastritis is stress and eating habits that can increase HCL in the stomach.[6]

Ulcer disease (Gastritis) is one of the diseases most often suffered by Indonesian people. According to WHO researchers, stomach ulcers suffered by Indonesians reach a range of 40.85% [8]. The incidence of gastritis in several regions in Indonesia is quite high with a prevalence of 274,396 cases of 238,452,952 inhabitants[7]. Based on Indonesia's health profile in 2011, Gastritis is one of the 10 most frequent diseases of inpatients in hospitals in Indonesia. The incidence of gastritis in several regions in Indonesia is quite high with a prevalence of 274,396 cases out of 238,452,952 inhabitants. Ulcer disease (gastritis) is often considered trivial, and habits in lifestyle and types of food that are not noticed. One snack is chips, which is classified as a type of crackers, which are foods that are dry, crispy, durable, practical, easy to carry and store, and can be enjoyed at any time [9]. Reviewing the efficacy of taro plants which can also be used as consumption food as well as medicinal plants because of the content in them. So it is necessary to create an innovative food processing creation that can be used as a healthy snack for the people of Indonesia, and the idea we propose is to make chips from taro leaves while testing them on ulcer disease. Of course with the presence of taro leaf chips can minimize the people who have ulcer disease, besides that the natural resources that are less optimal for use such as taro leaves can produce an effort. However, the lack of taro also has a lot of gum which can make itchy when eating it [10]. The itching was not caused by a chemical reaction in sensitive skin but because of mechanical phenomena. Itching that stimulates the oral cavity and skin caused by the presence of small needles in the form of fine needles composed of calcium oxalate called rhapsid. The Rhapsid is enclosed in a capsule surrounded by mucus (Richana, 2012). So to minimize and eliminate itching from taro leaf preparations. Need to be given additional mixtures, namely honey in the process.

Based on the description above, the researcher is interested in conducting a research entitled “*Taro Leaf Chips With Honey Addition to Heal Gastric Disease*”. This paper focuses on how taro leaf chips can be consumed by the community and has benefits for relieving pain in the stomach (gastritis).

2. Research Methods

2.1 Time and Place

The study was conducted in two places, specifically, at Bogor Agricultural Institute and SMK N 3 Central Jakarta. From August to September.

2.2 Method

The method used in this study was experimental, Organoleptic Testing was carried out by 15 students. Organoleptic properties which include hedonic tests on color, aroma, texture and taste and the conclusion of the most preferred products. For the conclusion analysis of the preferred product was done by calculating the percentage of the number of panelists who most like the product that tested. In addition, the taro chips were tested for safety by using 2 mice fed with taro leaf chips. Seeing the security seen from the consistency of the phases and the reaction of the mice. These chips also test efficacy in some people who suffer from ulcer disease. The ingredients used are taro leaves, honey, garlic, salt, hazelnut, water, vegetable oil. The tools used in this study were basins, knives, scissors, plates, trays, pans, bowls, scales, frying pans, stoves, spatulas.

Table 1. Composition of substances contained in 100 grams of taro leaf chips

Nutrient Content	Units	Taro Leaves
Energy	Kal	71
Protein	Gram	4,1
Fat	Gram	10,2
Fiber	Gram	2,5
Calcium	Mg	302
Phosphor	Mg	47
Iron	Mg	225
Vitamin B1	Mg	0,11
Vitamin C	Mg	163
Vitamin A	IU	10395
Polyphenols	Gram	70,0

2.3 Data Analysis

Financial analysis was conducted to see the feasibility of processing lung flavored spinach chips. The analysis used is Gross B / C, where the business was considered feasible if the Gross B / C value was more than one. The formulation of Gross B / C is (Kasijadi and Suwono 2001):

$$\text{Gross B/C} = \frac{P \times Q}{B_i}$$

Information :

P : Production Price (Rp/Kg)

Q : Production Result (kg/ha)

B_i : Production Costs to i (Rp/ha)

Figure 1. Processing Process for Taro Leaf Chips

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Organoleptic Test Result

The results of the analysis obtained from the hedonic test (preference) of 15 students included the parameters, aroma, taste and general preference listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Organoleptic Test Result

Type of Testing	Assessment Level	
	Like	Don't like
1. Aroma	70%	30%
2. Taste	73,3%	226,7%
3. Texture	55%	45%
4. Fondness	60%	40%

3.1.1 Aroma

Aroma is one of the key variables, because in general the taste of consumers towards food products is largely determined by the aroma. The smell of food determines the delicacy of food and the taste of food itself (Wellyalina et al. 2013). According to Kartika (1988), in the food industry the testing of aroma is considered very important because it can quickly produce an assessment of the product about the acceptance or rejection of the product. Taro leaf chips aroma is much influenced by the spices used namely garlic, coriander and candlenut. As many as 70% of 15 respondents liked the aroma of taro leaf chips.

3.1.2 Taste

Taste is a very important factor in determining panelists' acceptance or rejection of food (Kaswinarni 2015). Respondents' preference for the taste of all samples showed no significant difference. As many as 73.33% like the taste of these taro leaves, they respond to the taste of these taro leaves.

3.1.3 Texture

Texture is an element that shows the sense of surface material (material), which is intentionally created and presented in an arrangement to achieve the form, in real or pseudo forms. The texture of these taro leaf chips is the same as other chips.

In the Organoleptic Test Questioners panelists were also asked about the conclusions of the products they liked most. Of the 15 people, 60% like this chips, and as many as 40% say this product is creative.

3.2 Security Test Results

Based on experiments that have been given to two mice (*Mus Musculus*), the following data can be obtained:

Table 3. Safety Test Results for Taro Leaf Chips (*Colocasia esculenta*)

Day/Date	Object	Dose	Reaction	Stool Consistency	Stool Size
Sunday, September 17, 2017	Two mice (<i>Mus musculus</i>)	Each mouse (<i>Mus musculus</i>)	Act as usual	Shaped, soft, and dry	0,8 cm
Monday, September 18, 2017	Two mice (<i>Mus musculus</i>)	Each mouse (<i>Mus musculus</i>)	Looks a little more agile and active	Shaped, soft, slightly soft and slightly wet	1,3 cm
Tuesday, September 19 2017	Two mice (<i>Mus musculus</i>)	Each mouse (<i>Mus musculus</i>)	More agile than the previous day and very active	Shaped, soft, slightly soft, slightly wet, smelly	1,3 cm

Safety tests were carried out in two mice (*Mus musculus*) that were given the intake of taro leaf chips (*Colocasia esculenta*) on September 17, 2017. The intake was given as much as 5 grams at a time in two times a day with six repetitions within three days. The reaction of mice (*Mus musculus*) from day to day showed more positive reactions to the safety of taro leaf chips (*Colocasia esculenta*), because there were no negative effects during the observation. This can be evidenced by the behavior of the two mice (*Mus musculus*) which are increasingly agile and fecal consistency that tends to be stable as the consistency of feces of healthy mice in general and does not produce liquid feces. So there is no doubt about its security.

Test Efficacy

In the test efficacy this taking in the form of the revision of the effectiveness of such as the removal of pain in an ulcer by using chips leaves taro (*Colocasia esculenta*). Data obtained before and after consuming the processed product. Given the same intake of three samples as many as 30 grams once a meal, given after lunch and after dinner with the reason to be able to neutralize the food that has been consumed. In the third the previous week not eating chips sampelis taro leaves (*Colocasia esculenta*). In the next week after they were eating chips taro leaves (*Colocasia esculenta*) sampelis feel the positive effects are reduced relapse in ulcer disease experienced. The feces that were removed from all three samples were shaped, soft, somewhat liquid / soft, and wet this included normal feces, there were no negative effects of the three samples after consuming taro leaf chips (*Colocasia esculenta*).

2. Mrs. Nurcahyani data

Table 4. The results of the test and been approved efficacy Mrs. Nurcahyani

The Efficacy	Before Consume	After Consume
Day / Date	18 September 2017	23 September 2017
Frequency	1- 2 times in week	Not recur in this week
A recurrence of consistency	Pain	-

3. Mrs. Reni Yulianti Data

Table 5. The results of the test and been approved efficacy Mrs. Reni

The Efficacy	Before consume	After consume
Day / date	18 September 2017	23 September 2017
Frequency	2- 5 times in week	3 in on week
A recurrence of consistency	Pain	-

4. Miss Friska Ami Ardiyani Data

Table 6. The results of the test and been approved efficacy miss friska

The Efficacy	Before consume	After comsume
Day/ Date	18 September 2017	23 September 2017
Frequecy	2-3 times in week	1 times in week
A recurrence of consistency	Pain	Pain

3.4 Analysis of business feasibility

Analysis business feasibility processing chips leaves taro in addition to honey 50 ml. The sale of chips leaves the taro with a price of Rp. 12.000 of the packaging in order as far as officially noted for table 7. The results of the analysis taro chips leaves the feasibility of processing enterprises in addition to honey considered appropriate to do because it produces the gross b / c more than one .From analysis was , for the taro leaves 1 kg (accompanied by addition of material other) will produce taro chips leaves as many as 30 wrap . From the sale of , the company net income will be produced as much as Rp. 360.000, income of funds provided for the tribute of Rp. 152.000 to thirty of the packaging in order. The results of the study can be summed up as follows , on all treatment , for parameter color , the scent of , texture and taste the fruits of their is no different with plain

old mostly street and accepted by the community .So that it may become the household because food alternatives in preference to be acceptable to the panel both in terms of color , the scent of , texture and also flavored with favorite testing shows ranged from neutral or usual until like. Analysis chips taro processing enterprises in addition to honey indicates that effort is appropriate or profitable.

Table 7. The business feasibility of making chips leaves taro analysis

No	Description	Volume	Unit Cost (Rp)	The size of payments (Rp)
Expenses				
1	Taro leaf	1kg	25.000	25.000
2	Rice Powder	1 kg	10.000	10.000
3	Egg	1 kg	24.000	24.000
4	Garlic	2 ons	5.000	5.000
5	Coriender	2 ons	5.000	5.000
6	Salt		3.000	3.000
7	Pecan	2 ons	5.000	5.000
8	Water	100 ml		
9	Vegetable Oil	1 liter	21.000	21.000
10	Honey	50 ml	30.000	30.000
11	Gas		25.000	25.000
12	Packaging	20	2500	50.000
Total expenses				208.000
Income		30	12.000	360.000
Revenue (income – expenses)				Rp 152.000

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